

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Figure S1. Capillary β -hydroxybutyrate over the 3-hour measurement period segregated by sex
Data are presented as mean \pm SD with individual participant's data; Capillary beta-hydroxybutyrate (BHB) before (T0) and 3 hours (T180) after the consumption of exogenous ketone monoester

Figure S2. Correlation between the change in capillary blood BHB and plasma BHB–amino acid conjugates

A, B, C and D: Pearson correlation between the delta (T120-T0) of capillary beta-hydroxybutyrate (BHB) and delta (T120-T0) of BHB-amino acid conjugates (BHB-phenylalanine, BHB-valine, BHB-leucine, and BHB-methionine).

Figure S3. Hemodynamic changes over the 3-hour measurement period

Data are presented as box-and-whisker plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum values with individual participants' data; A: systolic blood pressure (SBP) before (T0) and 3 hours (T180) after the consumption of exogenous ketone monoester; B: diastolic blood pressure (DBP) before (T0) and 3 hours (T180) after the consumption of exogenous ketone monoester; C: heart rate in beats per minute (BPM) before (T0) and 3 hours (T180) after the consumption of exogenous ketone monoester.

Figure S4. Continuous heart rate over the 3-hour measurement period

Data are presented as mean \pm SD; BPM= beats per minute; time is presented in minutes, from the start of exogenous ketone consumption (0 minutes) to the three-hour mark (180 minutes).

Figure S5. Gastrointestinal symptoms following KME consumption over the 3-hour

Data are presented as box-and-whisker plots showing the median, 25th and 75th percentiles, minimum and maximum values with individual participants' data; A through E represent gastrointestinal symptoms, rated on a scale from 0 (no symptoms) to 10 (worst imaginable); F: the gastrointestinal (GI) composite score was calculated by averaging values from measures A through E into a single score; * Significant difference compared to baseline, as determined by Friedman ANOVA with Wilcoxon post-hoc tests.